

DIRECTIONS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL STUDIES OF RUSSIAN LINGUISTS

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The article elaborates different linguists' assumptions about phraseology. Despite the fact that numerous valuable research works and studies have been conducted on phraseology in Russian linguistics, the language examples we present under the name of the term syntactic phraseological construction have not been combined and studied under the name of a single term. The term syntactic phraseological construction itself can be considered new for Russian linguistics. Thus, phraseology with a sentence structure usually means clichés, sayings, proverbs, and phraseological sentences. However, there is also a group of expressions within phraseological sentences, which play an important role in grouping, studying them according to their composition, scope in the text, expression possibilities, and stylistic features. In general, defining syntactic phraseological constructions, determining their categorical qualities, and investigating the characteristics of these language units can be considered appropriate from the point of view of studying modern phraseology.

Keywords: phraseology, phraseological units, language units, typological relevance, main concept.

Introduction

In our opinion, the main factor of mastering any language perfectly is the deep knowledge of the phraseology of that language. Phraseology is the most difficult layer to master in the language. Since the phraseological units in the language are an expression of the history, customs, psychology and way of thinking of the people who are the bearers of the language, the linguistic research of the phraseological units in the language of any people, as a result, the history and ethnography of that people. The study of phraseological studies will help to clarify the historical development of that language, on the one hand, and the people who are the bearers of this language, on the other hand [1].

As we mentioned, although phraseology is a relatively young science, it has taken its place in the world of linguistics and has become the object of attention of many scientists - lexicologists, lexicographers, stylists, grammarians, literary scholars, ethnologists, folklorists. Undoubtedly, this interest is related to the wide character of phraseological units and the richness of their features. The rich nature of phraseological units provides ample opportunities to explore them in different directions [2].

Main part

Phraseology at the initial stage of its development is naturally separated from other scientific fields, trying to establish itself as an independent branch of linguistics. Nevertheless, any specific description of a phraseological phenomenon inevitably goes beyond the boundaries of one language and inevitably includes all existing languages practically available for observation at a given time. Kolshansky wrote: "it is necessary to build on the basis of the main dialectical contradiction, which consists in the fact that the description of a specific language is also the description of a general language" [5]. Having gained some experience in the phraseological analysis of stable and repeatable language units characterized by the presence of semantic transformation, phraseology rises to a new qualitative stage of its development.

Until recently, phraseology was poorly developed and began to emerge only in the 50s and 60s of XX century. The development of this branch of linguistics in Russian linguistics is associated with the name of Academician V. Vinogradov [3]. He dedicated a number of works to this problem. The abundance and diversity of phraseological units in the Russian language forces linguists to distinguish phraseology as a special branch of linguistics. Phraseological expressions, being indivisible and semantically whole, usually serve as a member of a sentence and are equivalent to a word, because they express one concept.

Only in the late 70s and early 80s, indicators of the potential universality of this or that phraseological phenomenon in the linguistic literature of XX century are, first of all, E.M. Malt'ho (1977) and Yu.P. Maltub (1982). The first attempts to form phraseological universals date back to the early 1980s and first of all V.D. is presented in the works of the linguists of the school on comparative and typological phraseology. The development of the science of linguistics itself requires the joint efforts of specialists in logical phraseology and typology. The typological relevance of phraseology can no longer be overshadowed. In the fundamental work of Dobrovolski, special attention is paid to the development of issues related to the problem of typological research of phraseology. For the first time in linguistics, Dobrovolski took decisive steps in forming the foundations of the structural and typological analysis of the phraseology of modern Germanic languages [4].

Based on the theoretical generalization of language problems related to the phenomenon of discreteness/connectedness of the formal-semantic structure of phraseological units and the linguistic-statistical analysis of the phraseological systems of German, English and Dutch languages, the direct dependence of the measure of regularity of the phraseological system on the degree of analyticity of the linguistic system has been fully confirmed.

The current state of linguistics allows us to express the existence of comparative phraseology as an independent and rapidly developing linguistic direction, where specific aspects of research, such as comparative-historical, comparative, structural-typological, intensive-typological, contrasting, have their own methods and tasks.

V.V. Vinogradov's work "The Russian Language", published in 1947, the scientist identified three types of phraseological units: phraseological compounds, phraseological associations, phraseological adhesions.

The fourth group of expressions is emphasized - phraseological expressions. Phraseological expressions do not differ from free expressions in terms of the nature of the general meaning connection with words.

The analysis of phraseological units, their semantics, the connection of their semantics with the semantics of individual words shows that these units are directly related to the lexical system, organically enter it and complete it. Most of the Russian phraseological units belong to one or another word class.

In the development of the phraseological theory of Russian linguistics at the end of XX and XXI centuries, first of all, it should be noted that in local linguistics the language itself has changed to describe phraseological units, which are now more often called phrasemes.

In the theory of Russian phraseology, the least studied at present are phraseological units or plural expressions with a sentence structure. It is generally accepted that "set sentences are equivalent to ordinary sentences due to their semantic and grammatical nature, as a result, they are opposed to phraseological units, i.e. phrasemes, by the structure of phrases and word combinations along the line of communicative (non-nominative) - non-communicative (nominative)". Such a view seems overly categorical and requires significant scrutiny and clarification regarding all types and types of UV. Currently, the postulate about the relationship between language and culture has become an axiom. The most important task at the current stage of the development of linguistics is to understand this interaction aimed at defining culture, based on the determination of the components reflected in the semantics of linguistic units and conveying knowledge about the world broken from the prism of the national language, as well as the methods of such scientific research.

The attention of modern linguistics is focused on man as his mother tongue, that is, a direction such as anthropocentrism comes to the fore. The relationship between the components of the "Man - language" dyad is considered in two aspects: man as a subject who understands and evaluates the world through language, and man as an object of description and evaluation through language units. In recent years, more works dedicated to the description of the human image in language appear.

Phraseology began to be associated more and more with linguocognitology, linguoculturology. This Alefirenko, O.A. Voronkova, L.G. It is proved by the works of Zolotykh and others. However, a number of questions remain that have not been fully studied by

modern linguists. Phraseology still remains as a complex science and a linguistic science that requires extensive knowledge from the researcher.

It can be considered a generally accepted opinion that phraseological units are organized according to phrase and sentence models, but differ from the latter either by the "integrity of nominations" or by the special nature of the meanings of lexical components.

Such a lexical-semantic approach to the problems of distinguishing phraseological expressions and variable combinations of words can be explained by the fact that their external similarity (formed separately) is obvious, and the differences do not seem to allow distinguishing purely structural regularities. Between phraseological expressions and combinations of words, for example, when distinguishing between a phrase and a complex word, certain structural regularities can be relied on. But despite the relationship between the syntactic and lexical levels of the language, each of them has its own elements and rules for their organization. Undoubtedly, all phraseological units were created on the basis of specific phrases and sentences. However, most phraseological units coincide in form with the types of existing word combinations. The difference is that variable combinations of words are organized according to structural models at the syntactic level of the language, while phraseological combinations have lost the ability of syntactic modeling to one degree or another.

Phraseology as a linguistic science attracts the attention of more researchers. If in the twenties the question of separating phraseology into a special field of linguistics was raised for the first time.

The classification analysis of the modern development of phraseology allows to identify clearly formed areas of research in this linguistic discipline, namely:

1. Morphological and grammatical features of phraseological units;
2. Structural types of phraseological units;
3. Semantics of phraseological units;
4. phraseological nomination;
5. The specificity of the relationship of phraseological units with their components and complex words;
6. Cognitive approach to the study of phraseological meaning;
7. Stylistic function of phraseological units;
8. Sources of phraseological units and ways and methods of phraseologicalization;
9. Phraseology of different regional variants of the language;
10. Phraseography;
11. Phraseological derivation;
12. Author's phraseological idiosyncrasy;
13. Functional-communicative features of phraseological units;
14. Linguistic aspect of phraseology and national-cultural specificity of phraseological units;
15. phraseological terminology;
16. Sociolinguistic aspect of pragmatic functions of phraseological units;
17. Genre, style, artistic and other problems of phraseological translation;

18. Phraseology in the context of subculture;
19. The linguodidactic aspect of phraseology;
20. Modeling problem in the field of phraseology;
21. The problem of system relations of phraseological units

It is necessary to add a point to the above list about the comparative study of phraseological units of different languages as the most intensively developing direction in phraseology, because in the late 60s, work on the aspect of comparative phraseological studies had just begun. Among them M.A. Pekler (1967) A.S. Rahimov (1968), L. Ya. Orlovskaya (1968) studies phraseology and their work in some aspects has not lost its relevance even today [6].

The aim of this article is a global description of Russian phraseology (idioms) in communicative and pragmatic aspects. This goal is defined and solved in the following main tasks:

1. To justify the need to analyze Russian idioms in the communicative-pragmatic aspect as concrete units designed to serve the communicative sphere of language and speech.
2. To determine the linguistic functions of phraseological units.
3. To characterize the features and structure of phraseology.
4. To characterize the main semantic-grammatical (partial) categories of phraseological units in the communicative aspect.
5. To characterize the semantics of idioms in the onomasiological aspect.
6. To give an ideographic description of idioms: a) to define the subject and tasks of phraseological ideography, b) to characterize and structure the main phraseological fields.

These studies differ in that, when conducting a comparative analysis of linguistic phenomena, the authors consider the mother tongue as the value by which the phraseological facts of the foreign language are determined or described.

Phraseology at the initial stage of its development is naturally separated from other scientific fields, trying to establish itself as an independent branch of linguistics. However, any specific description of a phraseological phenomenon inevitably goes beyond the boundaries of one language and inevitably includes all existing languages that are practically available for observation at a given time. As Kolshansky points out, "The study of a separate language system" "needs to be built on the basic dialectical contradiction that the description of a particular language is also the description of a general language. Having gained some experience in the phraseological analysis of stable and repeatable language units characterized by the presence of semantic transformation, phraseology rises to a new qualitative stage of its development.

The time has come when, on the one hand, descriptive linguistics, in this case both classical and field phraseology, finds its way in typological generalizations. And on the other hand, as the history of the development of linguistic typology shows, there is an increasing need to use phraseological materials to create

the most complete typological model of the language possible.

There are three main types of phraseological units: idioms, phraseological units and phraseological units.

Phraseological units (idioms) are stable expressions that have meaning only in their unchanging form. When you replace or rearrange the words, the meaning of the idiom will be lost.

Phraseological combinations are fixed but flexible expressions, the meaning of which is determined by separate keywords. In this case, non-key words can be replaced by synonyms. Example: you can "die of love" or "you can die of pleasure" - the meaning of both expressions is clear.

Two directions of research in modern linguistics

Summarizing the broad ideas about phraseology, we can note the following. Two directions of research in modern linguistics have clearly emerged.

The first direction is based on the recognition that the phraseological unit is a linguistic unit consisting of words, that is, by its nature, a word combination. At the same time, some scholars express the opinion that the object of phraseology is all concrete expressions that are actually possible in a given language, regardless of the qualitative differences between them. So, for example, Kopylenko says: "Phraseology covers all ... lexeme combinations, including "free" word combinations, that exist in a given language [7].

On the other hand, within the limits of this direction, the object of phraseology is recognized only by certain categories and groups of word combinations that stand out from all possible ones in speech with their special originality. The composition of such units in the language is determined depending on what features are taken into account when defining such expressions. Only these "special" phrases can be called phraseological units. Despite the conventionality of concepts and related differences, phraseology is usually said to represent:

1. As the phraseology of the language in the "broad" sense of the word, including completely rethought phrases with unreinterpreted component words. An example of such a "broad" understanding of the scope and composition of phraseology is the point of view of V.L. Arkhangelsky, O.S. Akhmanova, N.M. Shansky.

2. As phraseology of the Russian language in the "narrow" sense of the word, including only completely rethought expressions. Among the works that reflect this understanding of the scope and composition of the phraseology of the Russian language, there are, for example, articles by V. P. Zhukov.

In both cases, the verbal nature of the phraseological unit, as well as the lexeme character of its components, are not questioned by these scholars. It is recommended to consider the phraseological unit as a contamination of the features of the word and phrase, emphasizing the homonymy of the phraseological unit and the phrase structurally related to it.

Phraseologies of New Testament origin, with their figurative system, lively expressiveness and deep spiritual content, are never a frozen mass of obsolete words. In our work, we tried to lift the veil of traditional views

on this layer of the Russian vocabulary, to at least give an overview of its current state against the background of general theoretical information on phraseology. Certain conclusions can be drawn as a result of the analysis of a number of scientific-journalistic works and lexicographic sources.

Conclusion

Despite the fact that numerous valuable research works and studies have been conducted on phraseology in Russian linguistics, the language examples we present under the name of the term syntactic phraseological construction have not been combined and studied under the name of a single term. Note that the term syntactic phraseological construction itself can be considered new for Russian linguistics. Thus, phraseology with a sentence structure usually means clichés, proverbs, sayings, and phraseological sentences. However, there is also a group of expressions within phraseological sentences, which play an important role in grouping, studying them according to their composition, scope in the text, expression possibilities, and stylistic features. In general, defining syntactic phraseological constructions, determining their categorical qualities, and investigating the characteristics of these language units can be considered appropriate from the point of view of studying modern phraseology.

In the development of phraseology, as we have seen, great prospects are opening up, focusing on the extensive study of functional language in interaction with it, recently intensified research in the field of onomasiology, nomination theory, linguistic pragmatics, functional grammar and wider communicative linguistics.

As for Russian phraseology (idioms), it has not yet been the object of comprehensive research in the communicative aspect. This determines the relevance of the topic of this work. The scientific topic we advance is dictated by the logic of the development of linguistics itself, which has become a comprehensive analysis of language as the main means of communication of people today.

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